

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN COMPOSITES INITIATED BY MATRIX CRACKING

D. T. G. Katerelos^{1,2} and J. Varna¹

¹Luleå University of Technology
SE 971 87, Luleå, Sweden

d.katerelos@gmail.com, Janis.Varna@ltu.se

² Ionian Islands Technological Educational Institute, Sound Engineering Department
St Typaldou ave., GR-28200, Lixouri, Greece

SUMMARY

Stress state in the vicinity of transverse crack tip is investigated using an analytical variational model based on principle of minimum complementary energy. Knowing the stress concentration factor's (SCF) values at the tip of the crack, the possibility of new damage modes initiation is examined. SCF is recalculated taking into account the possible local stiffness reduction due to new modes of damage.

Keywords: Damage, matrix cracking, delamination, fibres breakage, analytical model

INTRODUCTION

Understanding of damage mechanisms and damage development during composite structures service life is of outstanding significance regarding safety and sustainability. Matrix cracking called also transverse and intralaminar cracking has been the subject of wide research during the last forty years. Several approaches and solutions have been applied to investigate the cracking initiation and growth and its effects on material behaviour. The approaches span from micromechanics to continuum damage mechanics [1-3]. Matrix cracking results in redistribution of the internal stress state in the plies, especially in the vicinity of cracks. Experimental studies have been conducted in order to quantify the stress and strain redistribution within the 0° layer of a general $[0^\circ/\theta^\circ]_s$ laminate due to cracking of the θ° layer, using Raman spectroscopy [4-5].

Analytical modelling of the stress or strain state in cracked composites has been aimed mainly to laminates thermoelastic properties reduction [6-8]. While the success of those methods depends strongly on the accurate stress analysis, the interest in the stress distribution within the layer supporting the cracked lamina (-e) has been low. The most commonly used models like the shear-lag [9] and the Hashin's variational [10] models, do not calculate the stress concentration factor (SCF) appearing at the crack front and the stresses redistribution in the intact laminae of a damaged composite is considered independent of the thickness coordinate. The SCF has been rendered by both experimental [5] and finite elements results, but only a few analytical models have been suggested to account for it [11].

In the present paper, a theoretical model based on complementary energy minimization is proposed to describe the stress distribution in a $[0/90]_s$ GFRP laminate with cracks in 90-layers. A two-dimensional stress state in the x-z plane, where x is the loading axis and z is the through the thickness direction, is considered. The model can take into account the

secondary forms of distributed damage, that include broken fibres and local matrix failure such as local delaminations, arising within the intact layers adjacent to cracked ones. Secondary damage is located at a region close to the plies interface and is initiated by the SCFs of both normal and shear stress components at the crack tip, thus the intact layers are divided into a chosen number of sub-layers. Stresses and the corresponding SCFs distributions are calculated as a function of the distance from the crack tip assuming that the matrix cracks did not cause secondary phenomena in 90-layer. The shape of the stresses distribution is described by functions with unknown shape parameters which are determined by minimizing the complementary energy of a repeating element of the laminate between two transverse cracks. Thus calculated stresses are used in a statistical failure criterion regarding the fibres and a quadratic failure criterion (QFC) regarding the isotropic matrix to identify and quantify damage modes arising in each intact layer sub-layer. Finally, by reducing the sub-layers properties, correspondingly to those secondary damage modes, the actual SCFs distributions are drawn.

Figure 1. Geometrical characteristics of the repeating element.

MODELLING

Geometrical Description

A repeating element, shown in Fig. 1, of length $2l_0$ between two transverse cracks in 90° layer of the laminate is considered. Dimensionless normalized coordinates x , z are introduced by dividing them with the 90° -layer half-thickness, (t_{90}) . The normalized crack spacing is $2a = 2l_0/t_{90}$. The 0° layer of thickness t_0 that supports the 90° layer of normalized half-thickness $t_{90} = 1$ is assumed partially damaged especially in the vicinity of the cracks and hence its elastic properties depend on the distance from the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. In order to account for the properties degradation the 0° layer is divided into sub-layers with different elastic properties, determined in a separated routine described later and the properties reduction (i.e. degree of damage) is larger in sub-layers closer to the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. Numbers are assigned to sub-layers, assigning the 90° layer $k = 0$. The 0° sub-layers are numbered as $k = 1$ to N with k increasing with the distance from $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. The k -th sub-layer interface coordinates are denoted by z_k and z_{k-1} . The

normalized coordinate of the outer surface is z_N . The sub-layer thickness is $t_0^{(k)} = z_k - z_{k-1}$

Obviously $t_0 = \sum_{k=1}^N t_0^{(k)}$ while laminate's half-thickness is $\frac{h}{2} = t_0 + t_{90}$.

Loading and Boundary Conditions

Loading consists of a thermal and a mechanical component. The mechanical part is an average far field stress σ_{x0} . The thermal component is the result of the mismatch between the laminae thermal expansion coefficients and the temperature difference ΔT . At the outer boundary both normal transversal and shear interlaminar stresses should be zero, while due to symmetry, interlaminar shear stress component on the mid-plane has to be zero. Upper index denotes the relevant sub-layer.

$$\sigma_{xz}^N \Big|_{z_N} = \sigma_{zz}^N \Big|_{z_N} = 0 \text{ and } \sigma_{xz}^{90} \Big|_{z=0} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Interlaminar normal and shear stress continuity at all interfaces are written as:

$$\sigma_{xz}^{90} \Big|_{z=1} = \sigma_{xz}^1 \Big|_{z=1}, \quad \sigma_{xz}^k \Big|_{z_k} = \sigma_{xz}^{k+1} \Big|_{z_k}, \quad \sigma_{zz}^{90} \Big|_{z=1} = \sigma_{zz}^1 \Big|_{z=1}, \quad \sigma_{zz}^k \Big|_{z_k} = \sigma_{zz}^{k+1} \Big|_{z_k}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (2)$$

Traction free conditions on crack surfaces are expressed by the form:

$$\sigma_{xx}^{90} \Big|_{x=\pm a} = \sigma_{xz}^{90} \Big|_{x=\pm a} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Finally, the integral force equilibrium has to be satisfied in any cross section $x = \text{const}$.

Since the stress problem is formulated in tractions, the principle of complementary energy minimization can be used for stress determination: the most accurate admissible stress-state that automatically satisfies the equilibrium equations and the formulated conditions in tractions (1) to (3) is the one giving the lowest complementary energy. The particular shape of stress distribution is result of the minimization routine.

Stresses Distribution

Equilibrium equations are automatically satisfied if the stresses corresponding to the 2-D problem described, are defined using the *stress function*, Φ , as follows:

$$\sigma_{xx} = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2}, \quad \sigma_{zz} = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2}, \quad \sigma_{xz} = -\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial z} \quad (4)$$

For the 90°-layer the Φ is chosen to correspond to Hashin's assumptions [10-11]

$$\Phi^{90} = \sigma_{x0}^{90} \left[\frac{z^2}{2} - \psi(x) \left(\frac{z^2}{2} + A^* \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

where, the $\psi(x)$ function should be determined. In (5) σ_{x0}^{90} is the laminate (CLT) theory stress in the 90° layer. From (4) and (5) the stresses in the 90° layer are:

$$\sigma_{xx}^{90} = \sigma_{x0}^{90} [1 - \psi(x)], \quad \sigma_{zz}^{90} = -\sigma_{x0}^{90} \psi''(x) \left(\frac{z^2}{2} + A^* \right), \quad \sigma_{xz}^{90} = \sigma_{x0}^{90} \psi'(x)z \quad (6)$$

According to the assumptions, the axial stress in the 90° layer is independent on the z -coordinate. Consequently, the shear stress σ_{xz}^{90} varies linearly with z -coordinate, while σ_{zz}^{90} is parabolic. Thus the boundary condition (1) is automatically satisfied.

In the k -th sub-layer the shape of the complex stress components distribution along the z -coordinate is described by an initially unknown functions $\varphi_k(z)$:

$$\Phi^k = \sigma_{x0}^k \frac{z^2}{2} + \sigma_{x0}^k \varphi_k(z) \psi(x), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (7)$$

Here σ_{x0}^k is the CLT stress in this sub-layer, while $\psi(x)$ and $\varphi_k(z)$ are functions to be determined. Using equations (4) and (7) the stress components are:

$$\sigma_{xx}^k = \sigma_{x0}^k + \sigma_{x0}^{90} \varphi_k''(z) \psi(x), \quad \sigma_{zz}^k = \sigma_{x0}^{90} \varphi_k(z) \psi''(x), \quad \sigma_{xz}^k = -\sigma_{x0}^{90} \varphi_k'(z) \psi'(x) \quad (8)$$

The boundary conditions for the σ_{xz} (1) and (2) result in the following conditions for φ_k' :

$$\varphi_N'(z_N) = 0, \quad \varphi_1'(1) = -1, \quad \varphi_k'(z_k) = \varphi_{k+1}'(z_k), \quad k = 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (9)$$

It can be shown that using functions which satisfy (9) the integral force equilibrium is automatically satisfied. Applying stress expressions (6) and (8) in (1) and (2):

$$\varphi_N(z_N) = 0, \quad \varphi_1(1) = -\frac{1}{2} - A^*, \quad \varphi_k(z_k) = \varphi_{k+1}(z_k), \quad k = 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (10)$$

The traction free boundary conditions at crack surfaces (3) lead to:

$$\psi(\pm a) = 1 \text{ and } \psi'(\pm a) = 0 \quad (11)$$

Complementary Energy

The expression for complementary energy of a laminate element shown in Figure 1 is:

$$V = U + 2 \Delta T \alpha_2 \int_0^{l+a} \int_{-a}^a (\sigma_{xx}^{90} + \sigma_{xx}^{90}) dx dz + 2 \Delta T \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_{k-1}-a}^{z_k} \int_{-a}^a (\sigma_{xx}^k \alpha_x^k + \sigma_{zz}^k \alpha_z^k) dx dz \quad (12)$$

where, ΔT is the temperature difference, α_2 , is the transverse thermal expansion coefficient of the unidirectional composite, and α_x and α_z are the thermal expansion coefficients of the 0° layer in x and z directions, respectively. U is the strain energy defined as:

$$U = 2 \int_{-a}^{l+a} \int W_{90} dx dz + 2 \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \int W_k dx dz \quad (13)$$

where

$$W_{90} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{(\sigma_{xx}^{90})^2}{E_2} + \frac{(\sigma_{zz}^{90})^2}{E_2} + \frac{(\sigma_{xz}^{90})^2}{G_{23}} - \frac{2\nu_{23}}{E_2} \sigma_{xx}^{90} \sigma_{zz}^{90} \right\}, \quad W_k = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{(\sigma_{xx}^k)^2}{E_1^k} + \frac{(\sigma_{zz}^k)^2}{E_2^k} + \frac{(\sigma_{xz}^k)^2}{G_{12}^k} - \frac{2\nu_{12}^k}{E_1^k} \sigma_{xx}^k \sigma_{zz}^k \right\} \quad (14)$$

In (14) $E_1, E_2, G_{23}, \nu_{23}$ are the elastic constants of the 90° layer in local axes, while $E_1^k, E_2^k, G_{12}^k, \nu_{12}^k$ are the elastic constants of k -th sub-layer in its local axes.

The expressions for stresses given by (6) and (8) have to be substituted into the equations (12)-(14) and formally integrated over z (assuming that the shape of $\varphi(z)$ is known). Following straightforward and tedious routine similar to described in [11] the following expression of the complementary energy to be minimized is obtained:

$$V = V_0 + (\sigma_{z0}^0)^2 \left\{ \int_{-a}^a [C_{00} \psi^2 + C_{02} \psi \psi'' + C_{22} (\psi'')^2 + C_{11} (\psi')^2] dx \right\} \quad (15)$$

Constants C_{ij} , ($i, j = 0, 1, 2$) in (15) are defined as follows:

$$C_{00} = \sum_{k=0}^N I_1^k, \quad C_{22} = \sum_{k=0}^N I_2^k, \quad C_{11} = \sum_{k=0}^N I_3^k, \quad C_{02} = \sum_{k=0}^N I_4^k, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N \quad (16)$$

In (16) I_i^0 ($i = 1 - 4$) depend on the assumed z -distribution of stresses in the 90° layer:

$$I_1^0 = \frac{I}{E_2}, \quad I_2^0 = \frac{I}{E_2} \left(\frac{I}{20} + \frac{A^*}{3} + (A^*)^2 \right), \quad I_3^0 = \frac{I}{G_{23}}, \quad I_4^0 = -\frac{2\nu_{23}}{E_2} \left(\frac{I}{6} + A^* \right) \quad (17)$$

Constants I_i^k ($i = 1 - 4$) depend on the shape of stress distribution in the k -th sub-layer:

$$I_1^k = \frac{I}{E_1^k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} [\varphi_k''(z)]^2 dz, \quad I_2^k = \frac{I}{E_2^k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} [\varphi_k(z)]^2 dz, \quad (18)$$

$$I_3^k = \frac{I}{G_{12}^k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} [\varphi_k'(z)]^2 dz, \quad I_4^k = -\frac{2\nu_{12}^k}{E_1^k} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \varphi_k(z) \varphi_k''(z) dz, \quad k = 1, \dots, N$$

Solution of the Stress Distribution Problem

Function which minimizes equation (15) has to satisfy the differential equation [10]:

$$C_{22} \psi'''' + (C_{02} - C_{11}) \psi'' + C_{00} \psi = 0 \quad (19)$$

and the boundary conditions given by (11). The solution for C_{ij} values corresponding to elastic constants for polymer matrix composites is of the form:

$$\psi = A_1 \cosh(\alpha x) \cos(\beta x) + A_2 \sinh(\alpha x) \sin(\beta x) \quad (20)$$

$$A_1 = \frac{2[\alpha \cosh(\alpha a) \sin(\beta a) + \beta \sinh(\alpha a) \cos(\beta a)]}{\alpha \sin(2\beta a) + \beta \sinh(2\alpha a)}, \quad A_2 = \frac{2[\beta \cosh(\alpha a) \sin(\beta a) - \alpha \sinh(\alpha a) \cos(\beta a)]}{\alpha \sin(2\beta a) + \beta \sinh(2\alpha a)} \quad (21)$$

$$\alpha = q^{1/4} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad \beta = q^{1/4} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad \tan(\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{4q}{p^2} - 1} \quad (22)$$

while constants p and q depend on the C_{ij} constants by the following expressions

$$p = \frac{C_{02} - C_{11}}{C_{22}}, \quad q = \frac{C_{00}}{C_{22}} \quad (23)$$

The solution (20)-(23) corresponds to the minimum of complementary energy in the framework of the used assumptions. This minimum value is given by [11]

$$V_{\min} = V_0 + 2(\sigma_{x0}^0)^2 C_{00} \frac{2\alpha\beta}{\alpha^2 + \beta^2} \cdot \frac{\cosh(2\alpha a) - \cos(2\beta a)}{\alpha \sin(2\beta a) + \beta \sinh(2\alpha a)} \quad (24)$$

The solution is based on the z -dependence of stresses given by functions $\varphi_k(z)$ which are still arbitrary. Even the numerical value of the minimum complementary energy (24) depends on this choice. The best distribution $\varphi_k(z)$ is found by comparing the values of the energy minima. Taking different $\varphi_k(z)$ will result in different solutions (given by the same functional form (20) with different values of V_{\min} (24)). The one which gives lowest value is the best. Thus the minimization becomes an optimization process.

There is an infinite number of ways how to choose $\varphi_k(z)$. The accuracy of the results depends on the success in finding forms that are physically justified. In this work, shape functions with arbitrary numerical parameters were chosen, which insure that the stress concentration is decreasing with the distance from the crack tip exponentially. The rate of decrease is characterized by parameters which are to be determined in the minimization routine. The shape functions used in this study are

$$\varphi_k(z) = B_k \frac{(z - z_{k-1})^2}{2} + D_k \exp(-\Delta_k(z - z_{k-1})), \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (25)$$

Using these exponential shape functions the solution and also the minimum value of the complementary energy V_{\min} depends on values of Δ_k for $k = 1, \dots, N$

$$V_{\min} = f(\Delta_1, \Delta_2, \dots, \Delta_N) \quad (26)$$

Numerical iterative methods can be used to find the set of Δ_k for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$ which gives the lowest value and hence the most exact solution.

Table 1 Elastic properties of the UD composite

Ply	Properties						
	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	α_1 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	α_2 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)
0°	43	13	4.69	0.3	0.42	$2.64 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$53.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stress Distribution in a cracked laminate

The presented analytical model was applied to determine the stress state at the crack tip of a cracked $[0/90]_s$ GFRP laminate. Layer thicknesses are, $t_{90} = 0.61\text{mm}$ and $t_0 = 0.64\text{mm}$. In the first calculation step the 0-layer properties were the same in all sub-layers of the layer (homogenized UD composite). Nevertheless, in order to keep the same model at all steps the 0° layer was divided into two sub-layers. The initial sub-layer interface was introduced at z where experimental SCF [6] reaches the value 1. Thus, the first sub-layer thickness, $t_0^{(1)}$ was 0.075 mm while the second, $t_0^{(2)}$ was 0.565 mm. Applying the boundary and continuity conditions, a set of $2N+2$ linear equations are formed for N sub-layers. The unknown constants resulting from the shape function (25) are $3N+1$. Thus, a total of $N-1$ constants should be determined using an iterative process based on the principle of complementary energy minimization. In the problem described above, this corresponds to a system of 6 equations for 7 unknowns. Thus the complementary energy minimization is used for the determination of 1 of the unknowns. The elastic properties for unidirectional composite (UD) are presented in Table 1. In accordance to experimental data [6] at strain 0.54% the crack density is 0.1 cracks/mm and the CLT stresses are: $\sigma_{x0}^{90} = 65.6\text{MPa}$ and $\sigma_{x0}^0 = 112.7\text{MPa}$ for the 90 and the 0 layers, respectively. Temperature difference is $\Delta T = -150^\circ\text{C}$. The lamina ν_{23} value in the isotropic 2-3 plane was calculated by a semi-empirical model [12].

Figure 2. SCF (σ_{xx}) and σ_{zz} distributions as a function of the z -distance.

The resulting SCF corresponding to the longitudinal stress, σ_{xx} , as a function of the laminate z -axis is presented in Fig. 2 a. The z -distance is normalized with respect to the 90° layer thickness. The maximum SCF value is predicted to be about 8 at distance $z = 1$, which is typical for this type of materials anisotropy. A rapid decay of the SCF with increasing z -distance is observed. Stress is reaching the external applied stress value at a normalized distance of 0.05. σ_{zz} distribution is presented in Fig. 2b. Normal stress σ_{zz} is compressive and takes a value of about 26 MPa. A rapid decay of the stress value is observed and stress practically diminishes at z less than 1.05. Diminishing of σ_{zz} is expected since no external stress is applied along the z -axis.

Experimental data for σ_{xx} , [5] are also shown in Fig. 2. The experimental data show much less steep stress decay than theoretical, implying that secondary damage is introduced into the first sub-layer of the 0° ply reducing its elastic properties.

Damage Identification – SCFs correction

In this study the two-parameter Weibull distribution is used to estimate the amount of broken fibres in the vicinity of the crack tip

$$F(\sigma_{xx}^f; b, c) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma_{xx}^f}{b}\right)^c\right], \quad b \geq 0, c \geq 0 \quad (27)$$

Figure 3. (a) Distribution of the fibres probability to failure, F . (b) Quadratic Criterion of Failure (QCF) values for possible matrix damage growth, as functions of z -distance

In equation (27) $F(\sigma_{xx}^f; b, c)$ represents the probability that the fracture stress is equal to or less than σ_{xx}^f , where the superscript f denotes that this stress is applied to the fibre. b is the Weibull scale parameter and c is the Weibull shape parameter, which are determined experimentally for each fibre material. In the present study the Weibull parameters values are taken from the literature for E-Glass fibres with 25mm gage length [13] and are equal to: $b=1079$ MPa and $c=15$. It can be assumed that $\sigma_{xx}^f = E_f \varepsilon_f$. ε_f is given by $\varepsilon_f = K \varepsilon_x$ where ε_x is the external applied strain $\varepsilon_x = 0.54\%$ and K is the SCF distribution calculated by the model. E-glass fibre is $E_f = 72.5 \text{ GPa}$, thus, $\sigma_{xx}^f = (391.5 \text{ MPa}) K$.

Distribution of the F probability as a function of z for the considered crack density $\rho = 0.1$ cr/mm is presented in Fig. 3a. F distribution represents the relative frequency of broken fibres at each z . Thus, for the modelling needs it is conservative to assume that the percentage of broken fibres within the 0° ply over a distance 0.05 is equal to the average F . Averaging the values of F over the hatched area shown in Fig. 3a results in an amount of 11% broken fibres.

The other secondary damage mode which could be present in the 0° ply is matrix related and depends on its strength. In order to investigate possible matrix related failures (yielding, splitting, delaminations, etc) a quadratic criterion of failure (QCF) is used.

QCF is given by the following relation (28) in the absence of σ_{xz} . The condition for failure is that the QCF should be equal or higher than 1.

$$F_{11}\sigma_{xx}^2 + F_{33}\sigma_{zz}^2 + 2F_{13}\sigma_{xx}\sigma_{zz} + F_1\sigma_{xx} + F_3\sigma_{zz} = 1 \quad (28)$$

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{XX'}, \quad F_{33} = \frac{1}{ZZ'}, \quad F_1 = \frac{1}{X} - \frac{1}{X'}, \quad F_3 = \frac{1}{Z} - \frac{1}{Z'}, \quad F_{13} = -\frac{1}{2}\sqrt{F_{11}F_{33}} \quad (29)$$

X and X' are the material strengths along x -axis in tension and compression respectively, Z and Z' along z -axis. Due to the matrix isotropy $Z = X$ and $Z' = X'$. Strengths values are taken from the literature [14] and are $X=Z=31\text{MPa}$ and $X'=Z'=118\text{MPa}$. In an isotropic matrix material elementary volume element the stress strain behaviour is given by the expression, $\underline{\varepsilon} = \underline{S}\underline{\sigma}$, where $\underline{\varepsilon}$ is the strain tensor, \underline{S} is the epoxy matrix compliance tensor and $\underline{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor. The matrix properties used were, $E_m = 3.5\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_m = 0.49$. Substituting these values to the stress strain relationship and solving with respect to the σ_{xx}^m and σ_{zz}^m , σ_{xz}^m proved to be zero, using the external applied strain $\varepsilon_x = 0.54\%$ the following equations resulted for the two stress components: $\sigma_{xx}^m = (24.95\text{MPa})K$, and $\sigma_{zz}^m = (12.29\text{MPa})K$, where K is the SCF calculated by the model. Applying QCF to an elementary volume in section $x = a$, using the stress distributions derived, the results are as shown in Fig. 3b. Thus, at the specific applied strain and damage level no matrix damage is expected.

As a next step a re-calculation is performed in order to include the determined secondary damage modes, i.e. broken fibres. Sub-layers thicknesses are selected based on the principle that their boundary is at the point where the calculated SCF becomes 1. Thus in this recalculation the sub-layers boundary is at $z = 1.05$. Longitudinal Young's Modulus, E_l is mostly dependent on the fibres and thus it was reduced by 11% in the first sub-layer since this is the broken fibres percentage calculated. The transverse and shear moduli and Poisson's ratios remain unchanged since no matrix damage appears. A recalculation of the SCF distribution is performed using the modified material properties, see Fig. 2. Comparing the theoretical predictions with the experimental data, a satisfactory fitting is observed. Thus, the presented method based on the proposed stress model and the described determination of possible secondary damage results in good predictions.

The new distribution of σ_{zz} is also drawn, in Fig. 3a to compare with the case where no secondary damage is present. Results show that secondary damage doesn't play significant role on the normal σ_{zz} stress distribution, except that the maximum value is reduced inconsiderably while their shapes are smoother.

CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model is proposed to explain the experimentally measured shapes of stress concentrations at the tip of transverse cracks in composite laminates. The model is used for the estimation of the extent of the secondary damage modes. The intact neighbouring layer is divided into a certain number of sub-layers with varying elastic properties corresponding to the extent of secondary damage. The shape of the stresses is described by functions with unknown shape parameters. These parameters are determined by a numerical complementary energy minimization process. The secondary damage arising

due to cracking are directly estimated using the theoretical predictions for the stresses assuming no damage in 0-layer and applying statistical model for prediction of the broken fibres percentage and for investigation of possible matrix damage using quadratic failure criterion. The secondary damage mode, i.e. broken fibres, is introduced into the stresses calculation by reduction of the corresponding elastic properties in the damaged zone. A corrected SCF distribution along the thickness of the laminate is in a good agreement with experimental data. Thus, the secondary damage and its effect on the material behaviour is predicted which could be useful in damage tolerance design.

References

1. Talreja R. Damage characterization by internal variables. In: Pipes RB and Talreja R, editors. *Damage mechanics of composite materials*. Composite materials series, vol. 9. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 1994
2. Varna J, Joffe R, Akshantala NV, Talreja R. Damage in composite laminates with off-axis plies. *Comp Sci Tech* 1999; 59(14): 2139-2147
3. Kashtalyan M, Soutis C. Analysis of Composite Laminates with Intra- and Interlaminar Damage. *Progr Aerosp Sci* 2005; 41(2): 152-173
4. Katerelos DTG, Lundmark P, Varna J, Galiotis C. Analysis of matrix cracking in GFRP laminates using Raman spectroscopy. *Comp Sci Tech* 2007; 67(9): 1946-1954
5. Katerelos DG, Galiotis C. Axial strain redistribution resulting from off-axis ply cracking in polymer composites. *App Phys Lett* 2004; 85(17): 3752-3754
6. Kashtalyan M, Soutis C. Mechanisms of internal damage and their effect on the behavior and properties of cross-ply composite laminates. *Int App Mech* 2002; 38(6): 641-657
7. Gudmundson P, Zang W. A universal model for thermoelastic properties of macro-cracked composite laminates. *Int Jnl Sol Struct* 1993; 30(23): 3211-3231
8. Lundmark P, Varna J. Constitutive Relationships for Laminates with Ply Cracks in In-plane Loading. *Int Jnl Damage Mech* 2005; 14(3): 235-261
9. Lim SG, Hong CS. Prediction of transverse cracking and stiffness reduction in cross-ply laminated composites. *Jnl Comp Mater* 1989; 23(7): 695-713
10. Hashin Z. Analysis of cracked laminates: a variational approach. *Mech Mater* 1985; 4(2): 121-136
11. Varna J, Berglund LA. Multiple Transverse Cracking and Stiffness Reduction in Cross-Ply Laminates. *Jnl Comp Tech Res* 1991; 13(2): 97-106
12. Philippidis TP, Theocaris PS. The Transverse Poisson's Ratio in Fiber Reinforced Laminae by Means of a Hybrid Experimental Approach. *Jnl Comp Mater* 1994; 28(3): 252-261
13. Brown EN, Davis AK, Jonnalagadda KD, Sottos NR. Effect of Surface Treatment on the Hydrolytic Stability of E – Glass Fiber Bundle Tensile Strength. *Comp Sci Tech* 2005; 65(1): 129-136
14. Tsai SW, Hahn HT. *Introduction to Composite Materials*. Westport: Technomic, 1980